

Factors Affecting Students Participating in Public English-Speaking Competition

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Abstract

The study aims to examine the factors affecting students' participation in public English-speaking competitions and explore the students' motivational strategies for participating in the competition. The sample of the study consisted of a hundred students enrolled at a private English school in the northwest of Cambodia. It employed both quantitative and qualitative methods. The questionnaire was used to examine why students rarely participate in public speaking competitions and the students' motivational strategies for participating in the competition. The semi-structured interview was utilized to obtain detailed information beyond the questionnaire responses. The results indicated that the linguistic factor was the most essential factor, followed by the physical factor and the environmental factor. Additionally, the findings showed that all the preparation strategies were effective, especially the linguistic improvement, which was the most significant strategy to motivate students to participate. It can be concluded that in order to participate in the English public speaking competition, students need to improve their linguistic skills and follow effective strategies.

Keywords: *factors, motivational strategies, public English-speaking.*

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Introduction

English is a worldwide language. According to Siddiqui, Qadri, & Chachar, (2023), with over 350 million people worldwide speak English as a first language and over 430 million speak English as a second language; it is quickly becoming the most commonly spoken language in the world. Since English is widely used throughout the world, it is spoken in all aspects of life (Schneider, 2020). It is useful in various fields, including business, academics, science, computing, education, transportation, politics, and entertainment (Alexander, 2020). Because of its importance, English is known as the international language, and it is used in communication worldwide (Grigoryeva & Zakirova, 2022).

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In Cambodia, Kroeun & Sophea (2023) stated that people are more interested in learning English as a second language. Learning English is necessary recently, and one of the purposes of learning is to develop the English language in four skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking (Thongsrirak, & Sarobol, 2018). Warsito (2023) mentioned that listening and reading are considered passive or receptive skills, whereas speaking and writing are considered active or productive skills (Apriliyanti, & Zain, 2014). The learners simply listen to or read the language without producing anything. However, the learners have to produce sentences on their own, and they require a lot of practice in grammar, vocabulary, sentence structure, and usage (Newton & Nation, 2020). As a result, speaking and writing are regarded as active or productive skills. Speaking skills is the most essential skill to acquire foreign or second language learning. Speaking is very important for people interaction because they speak everywhere and every day. Engaging in conversations can enhance learners' vocabulary, grammar, and writing skills by allowing them to express their thoughts, feelings, and stories using various language forms (Akhter, Haidov, Rana & Qureshi, 2020). Moreover, Samaeva (2023) asserted that students who are fluent in English have a better chance of receiving a better education, landing a good job, and getting promoted. Speaking is thought to be the most vital of the four skills. Despite having spent years studying English, many students are still unable to speak correctly and understandably (Dizon, 2020). Even after years of studying the language, learners find it difficult to speak in real-life situations when it is required. Consequently, in learning and teaching English for communication, speaking is only one of four language skills that are becoming increasingly important in human communication (Sabina, 2018).

With the importance of English speaking skills performance, many Cambodian EFL school directors organize public speaking competitions to promote confidence and commitment so that the students can become future-ready and confident individuals for future challenges (Seam, 2023). Additionally, it is designed to strengthen the quality of speaking skills and gives them the confidence to speak publicly in front of others while also holding them responsible for what they say (Nazeer-Ikeda, 2020). Although public speaking competition is strongly promoted and motivated, Cambodian students' participation is still ineffective (Lok, 2019). Most students rarely participate in public speaking competitions. The problem is there are not enough candidates to join the competition. Hence, the present study aims to explore the factors affecting students' participation in public English-speaking competition and examine the students' motivational strategies for participating in English Competition. Accordingly, two research questions were proposed, "What are the factors affecting students for participating in public English-speaking competitions?" and "What are the students' motivational strategies for participating in English public speaking Competitions?"

Literature Review

Definition of Speaking

Many scholars define speaking in different ways; however, they mean similar. Speaking is an activity that transfers information from the speaker to the listener. Speaking is the process of gathering information and accepting, producing, and processing it; therefore, it is valid and ready to be delivered as good communication. Speaking ability is the ability to speak fluently, which requires not only knowledge of linguistic features but also the ability to process information (Putra, 2017; Thornbury, 2012 & Derakhshan, Khalili & Beheshti, 2016). Moreover, speaking in a foreign language is

extremely difficult and takes a long time to develop (Jespersen, 2013). Learning to speak a foreign language is challenging because we must first understand the language itself, so it takes a long time to find someone who can speak English or develop the ability to speak. In short, speaking is defined as an interactive process of making meaning that includes producing, and processing information.

The Purpose of Speaking

People speak for different purposes. According to Billington & McKay (2022), speaking provides three important purposes: informing, entertaining, and persuading. The speaker informs the listener of everything they want or need, as well as ideas they wish to share. More importantly, speakers can express their feelings through speaking, and listeners can entertain them through this mutual communication. Likewise, everyone uses speaking to persuade others to participate in a particular activity. Speaking is concluded as a productive skill for developing students' speaking competence, which is used in human language to inform, entertain, and persuade listeners. Moreover, speaking is important to communicate about something or for other purposes (Ahmad, 2022). Speaking activities can be done in different ways, such as in the family, in the school, and in other environments. Speaking is also required while applying for jobs, conversing with others, or telling and describing something. However, learning to speak a foreign language needs more than just understanding its grammatical and semantic rules (Wahidul, 2022; Rokhimah, 2019). Therefore, with communication people can convey their ideas, notify news, and they can entertain people and persuade people well, so the listeners can understand well.

Public Speaking Anxiety

Anxiety occurs in every aspect of life including public speaking. Anxiety as apprehension or fear, as well as a state of uneasiness caused by the anticipation of something frightening (Perrotta, 2019 as cited in, Ting et al., 2021). Public speaking anxiety is the fear of delivering a public speech (Thongsrirak & Sarobol, 2018). There are several causes of public speaking fear, including insufficient experience, unfamiliarity with the audience or persons, and being the center of attention. People who are anxious about public speaking typically exhibit a wide range of symptoms, including beating, perspiration, diarrhea, muscle tension, stomach distress, and confusion (Thongmon & Rimkeeratikul, 2020). Martiningsih (2024) stated that approximately 85 percent of the general population reports experiencing some amount of nervousness when speaking in public. Researchers have explored and analyzed public speaking or stage fright since the mid-1930s (Susilawati, 2024). A depressed mind is the cause of most anxiety (Puri & Astuti, 2021). When speakers need to deliver their speeches in front of a large audience, their physical or emotional response is important in creating public speaking anxiety.

Not all students are able to speak in public. Students' lack of confidence is one of the reasons they struggle when speaking in front of an audience. Anxiety related to public speaking decreases with a person's level of self-confidence. Yogyakarta (2021) investigated the relationship between anxiety and student confidence when speaking in public. The findings indicated a correlation between public speaking fear and self-confidence.

Factors Affecting Public Speaking Anxiety

Speaking in public is one of the most common and visible anxieties caused by the strong influence of psychological factors such as self-confidence, self-esteem, feeling frustrated and losing energy, because these are emotions under our control (Herwanto,

2013; Thongsrirak, 2018). Public speaking anxiety can occur in any situation, such as lack of public speaking skills, lack of a foreign language, an emotional proclivity to speak in public, and the situation of public speaking characteristics (Siregar, 2022; Thongsrirak, 2018). Bodie (2010) indicated that anxiety usually manifests itself when a speaker wishes to deliver a speech in public for fear of being judged by others. This was especially true when students were required to use English or communicate with foreigners (Thongsrirak, 2018). Although the speakers were aware of their anxiety, it is irrational. They were unable to overcome their feelings of anxiety, depression, and frustration. Many studies found that speaking anxiety caused by limited grammar, vocabulary, English skills as well as pronunciation (Alazeer & Ahmed, 2023). Speakers were stressed and nervous when they received negative feedback from the audience (Hutabarat & Simanjuntak, 2019; Thongsrirak, 2018). An anxiousness or fearfulness was caused by the expectancy of something threatening. Anxiety is a common emotion in public speaking among both students and the public; it is a problem that affects everyone who speaks English or studies English as a second language (Osmond, 2013). English public speaking anxiety causes people to avoid anxiety-producing community or performance contexts, but when people are unable to avoid these situations, they experience anxiety and distress (Mardesich, 2023; Thongsrirak, 2018). Lindberg, McDonough & Trofimovich (2021) used convenience sampling to investigate the factors that contribute to public speaking anxiety and the strategies used to overcome the anxiety. This study used a quantitative method with a descriptive approach. The results revealed that both linguistic factors and physiological factors were significant and distinct. The students became nervous and anxious when they did not adequately prepare their speeches. While giving a public speech, students were unable to control their anxiety. As a result, postgraduate students used interesting topics to reduce their anxiety.

Motivational Strategies to Prepare for Public Speaking

Public speaking is not only about speaking in front of a crowd; it is also about how you get them to remember and understand what you say (Mufanti, Gestanti, & Nimasari, 2018). Being able to converse and interact with others effectively can assist you to be professional in your work. Therefore, public speaking involves giving a formal speech in front of the audience, but the speakers have to be able to help the audience grasp the information that they are hearing. There are five different forms of public speaking “Discovering the ‘Treasure of Public Speaking’”: impromptu speech, prepared speech, demonstration, presentation, and reports (Bandura, 1998, p.15). Impromptu speech is a type of speech that is done without prior planning but still needs to be performed in a professional manner. An impromptu speech requires the speaker to prepare their speech text right before they speak. A prepared speech is one strategy that has been prepared with the purpose of persuading and informing the audience about a subject that is relevant to the speaker's interests and experience (Simons, 2011). A demonstration is the presentation of a concept using visual aids with the intention of instructing the audiences (Pisarenko, 2017). Giving a presentation in front of an audience involves providing information or insight on a subject. Giving a report about anything you've done, like a committee report, is known as reporting (Meredith, 2021).

Self-efficacy in education is related to academic self-efficacy (Schunk, & DiBenedetto, 2022). Perceived self-efficacy in academics refers to someone's assessment of their ability to plan and carry out courses of action in order to achieve specific types of educational performance. Perceived self-efficacy in educational development refers to

how efficacy affects students' motivation to learn, effort in task execution, and achievement. Consequently, it can be concluded that perceived self-efficacy refers to someone's belief in their ability to execute subjects in order to improve their educational performance, and it also has an impact on their learning motivation, effort, and educational achievement. Perceived self-efficacy cannot be applied to all skills. It may differ from one to the other because each skill has different success criteria, but the scale of perceived self-efficacy is the same. It follows that the researcher's skill in examining the skill is a necessary condition for the successful criteria in perceiving self-efficacy. The success criteria for this study are specific to speech, so they may not apply to other skills, but the scale used to categorize high, moderate, and low self-efficacy levels is the same (Zhang, Ardasheva, & Austin, 2020). Hussain (2021) studied public speaking anxiety and the factors that contribute to it in Karachi. The findings revealed that students are afraid of public speaking and avoid giving their speeches. The study also demonstrated that public speaking anxiety can be reduced by rehearsing and practicing prior to presentations (Thongsrirak, 2018).

Materials and Methods

This Participants

The present study consisted of a hundred students enrolled in the Adults English Program (AEP) at a private English school in the northwest of Cambodia. AEP is an English part-time program for students aged 13 to 19. The participants are at the intermediate level and have studied English for at least three years. They are all native Cambodians who study English as a foreign language. The students were chosen purposively to participate in the study. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling strategy in which the researcher chooses certain participants with characteristics that provide the greatest information for achieving the research objectives (Campbell et al., 2020). The researcher chose this program and intermediate students because only English was allowed at the intermediate level, whereas at the beginner level, teachers and students were permitted to speak both Khmer and English (Each, 2019). Furthermore, the number of students at this level were appropriate for the study when compared to the advanced level because most advanced-level students are preoccupied with their work or degree studies, so they usually postpone or drop out (Each, 2019).

Research Instruments

The present study employed two research instruments: (1) Questionnaire to examine the reasons that students rarely participate in the public speaking competitions and the students' motivational strategies on participating in the competition, and (2) Semi-structured interview to obtain detailed information on questionnaire responses.

There are three parts in the questionnaire: (1) students' personal information (4 items), (2) the factors affecting students on participating public English-speaking competition (20 items), and (3) the students' motivational strategies on participating in English public speaking competition (12 items). The first section is about the students' profiles. Others were questioned about why students rarely participate in public speaking competitions and what factors influence students' participation in public speaking competitions. The questionnaire was adapted and modified from Thongsrirak and Staley, (2018) to examine students' opinions with five-point Likert scale ranged from 1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree.

The researchers created semi-structured interview questions consisting of 3 questions for fifteen students. The interview was conducted in the form of a face-to-face interview lasting 10 to 15 minutes. All interview responses were recorded to ensure that all information was kept completely and that it was allowed and permitted by the students.

Data Collection Procedures

The data was collected in both qualitative and quantitative to answer the research questions.

Before conducting the study, the researchers studied the overview of the part-time English program at a private school and decided to conduct the study there. The researchers requested information from the program coordinator regarding the program background, total number of classes, and levels. After that, the questionnaire was conducted with 100 students in the English part-time program in October 2022. The questionnaires must be completed by all students who were participating in the study.

A semi-structured interview was conducted after the students completed the questionnaire and continued to the next day depending on their comfort and convenience. Fifteen students were chosen to participate in the study to provide detailed information on questionnaire responses. The purpose of conducting a semi-structured interview is that they provided precise answers based on the questionnaire. Each interview lasted 10-15 minutes because the questionnaire contains all relevant information.

Data Analysis

The data in the study was analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative methods. The questionnaire responses of the factors affecting students on participating in English public speaking competitions and the students' motivational strategies for participating in English public speaking competition were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0 in terms of mean scores and standard deviation on a five-point Likert scales and were interpreted under the criterion below (adapted from Thongsrirak, 2018 and Staley, 2018):

- 4.51 to 5.00 = Strongly agree
- 3.51 to 4.50 = Agree
- 2.51 to 3.50 = Unsure
- 1.51 to 2.50 = Disagree
- 1.00 to 1.50 = Strongly Disagree

The data from the questionnaire was used for quantitative analysis, whereas the data from semi-structured interviews were used for qualitative analysis. The interview questions were analyzed as themes. All interviews were recorded, transcribed, and categorized by each question.

Results

Results from Questionnaire

The results of the present study fell in to the three factors: linguistic, physical, and environmental factor. Significantly, the most significant factor affecting students' participating in public English speaking was linguistic factor (Mean score = 3.81). The

second was physical factor (Mean score = 3.74), followed by environmental factor (Mean score = 3.73). It was clearly indicated that the three factors influenced students to participate in English public speaking competitions, but the linguistic factor is the most significant reason that affect their participation.

Table 1. Factors Affecting Students on Participating in English Public Speaking competition

Statements	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Physical Factors				
1. I am anxious and nervous as I prepare to give a speech.	100	3.8	1.092	High
2. I have difficulties sleeping the night before a speech.	100	3.55	1.038	High
3. My heart rate increases rapidly before I begin speaking.	100	4.05	0.869	High
4. Before giving a speech, I feel confused about the topic.	100	3.44	0.925	High
5. When I deliver a speech, my hands quiver.	100	3.86	0.841	High
6. I become so stressed while giving a speech that I forget facts that I am well-versed in.	100	3.83	0.865	High
7. When I make a mistake during a speech, it is difficult for me to concentrate on the parts that follow.	100	3.85	0.869	High
8. I get tense and anxious when I realize I only have a few minutes left in a speech.	100	3.72	0.922	High
9. I am unable to control my feelings of tension and anxiety while giving a speech.	100	3.63	0.950	High
10. I worry about looking foolish if I make mistakes.	100	3.75	0.947	High
Total		3.748	0.931	High
Linguistic Factors				
11. I'm afraid I'll use words that aren't appropriate for the situation.	100	3.64	0.938	High
12. I'm worried about pronouncing English words incorrectly.	100	3.76	0.878	High
13. I'm afraid I'll use incorrect English grammar.	100	3.93	0.913	High
14. I'm concerned that I won't be able to speak English fluently.	100	3.99	0.897	High
15. I am anxious that I won't know enough about the topic of the speech.	100	3.73	0.897	High
Total		3.81	0.904	High
Environmental Factors				
16. I become nervous when judges ask me questions on a topic about which I am unfamiliar.	100	4.1	0.823	High
17. I'm worried because I lack self-confidence.	100	3.98	0.791	High
18. I feel timid and uneasy.	100	3.67	0.726	High
19. I'm nervous because I'm afraid of the other competitors.	100	3.28	1.155	Moderate
20. I'm worried about getting negative feedback from the audience.	100	3.65	1.067	High
Total		3.73	0.912	High

Table 2 revealed students' motivational strategies on participating in English public speaking competition. The most effective strategies were item 6, "Before giving a public speech, watch videos of professional speakers to simulate their speech styles" (Mean score = 4.22), followed by item 5 "Consider the language features in the speech, such as grammar, vocabulary, and language expressions, carefully" (mean score = 4.20), and item 2 "Practice or rehearse the speech several times" (mean score = 4.13). All of these three strategies were at a high level.

The overall mean score of the students' motivational strategies on participating in English public speaking competition among the population was 4.01, which was "High" of interpretation. This demonstrated that all strategies were effective and motivated the students to participate in English public speaking competition.

Table 2. Students' Motivational Strategies on Participating in English Public Speaking Competition

Statements	N	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Prepare the content for the given topic of the speech carefully	100	4.01	0.689	High
2. Practice or rehearse the speech several times	100	4.13	0.734	High
3. Before giving a speech, evaluate and get to know the audience	100	3.08	0.804	Moderate
4. Plan and arrange the speech outline carefully	100	4.11	0.567	High
5. Consider the language features in the speech, such as grammar, vocabulary, and language expressions, carefully	100	4.22	0.651	Very high
6. Before giving a public speech, watch videos of professional speakers to simulate their speech styles	100	4.20	0.824	High
7. Edit the speech draft until the best speech possible	100	4.11	0.737	High
8. While giving a speech, manage your time effectively	100	4.08	0.646	High
9. Try to deliver the public speech in a comfortable and appropriate manner for the situation	100	4.04	0.634	High
10. Try not to be concerned about making mistakes during the speech.	100	4.00	0.696	High
11. Try to engage the audience by making eye contact with them and making friendly faces.	100	4.12	0.747	High
12. Control the movements, such as walking, standing, and moving, to demonstrate the confidence in public speaking	100	4.05	0.770	High
Total		4.01	0.708	High

Results from the Semi-structured Interviews

Students' Opinion toward English Public Speaking Competition

At the beginning of the interview, the students were asked about their opinions toward their participating in English public speaking competition. Twelve students responded positively that it was good. However, three students added that public speaking competition is hard and challenging. Students indicated the following examples:

- SS10:** “This event is really good because I can showcase my abilities, which I have already learned. Also, I can show the world that I have enough ability to compete with others.”
- SS12:** “An English public speaking competition is a great event for me. It allows me to speak, gain more knowledge, and showcase my abilities.”
- SS1:** “I think it’s a competition that is both good and challenging, as I give my speeches and compete with other. It is a great opportunity for me to showcase my passion and gain new experiences.”

Factors Effecting Students on Participating Public Speaking Competition

The students were asked about factors that affect their participation in public speaking competitions. Majority of students (N=13) responded that the linguistics factor is the major reason which causes them not to participate in speaking competition. The following statements are the confirmation of students’ answers:

- SS2:** “As we are a second language learner, we cannot speak fluently as the native speaker, so grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation are also the problem.”
- SS4:** “My speaking skills are not good. I cannot pronounce difficult words. I am afraid to speak in front of many people. For grammar, I don’t know why I often forget all the structure when I do the presentation even in the class.”
- SS10:** “I am poor at using grammar and vocabulary. I just know the simple words, and my pronunciation is not good at all.”

Moreover, some students (N=5) replied that the environmental factor affects their participating in the public English speaking competition as well. The following are some examples of what the students mentioned:

- SS8:** “I rarely hang out, so I’m afraid of people, especially in crowded places. I am also afraid of being judged by audience, candidates, and judges.”
- SS9:** “I am afraid of being on stage too. I am also afraid of being asked by a judge when I cannot answer.”
- SS15:** “I am not confident enough to face a crowd.”

Students (N=7) answered that Lack of confidence and anxiety are another problem. They are anxious about joining the competition. Here are a few examples of what the students said:

- SS7:** “I have some anxiety if I don’t prepare well.”
- SS11:** “To me, shyness and anxiety are the factors that I don’t join. I don’t believe myself.”
- SS15:** “Nervous and no experience. Lack of confidence, anxiety, and mental problem.”

Motivational Strategies for Participating in English Public Speaking

In this section, students were questioned regarding motivational strategies for participating in English public speaking. Some students (N=7) declared they need to improve their vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation, as stated in the following statements.

- SS2:** “Before the competition, I need to understand my topic, prepare the script, and learn more synonyms. Make sure I simplify it to make it more understandable. I used some applications for checking my grammar and vocabulary.”
- SS10:** “Be ready and prepare everything before the competition, such as checking all vocabulary and grammar in use.”
- SS14:** “Practice more, check grammar, words, and how to pronounce before giving the speech.”

Other students (N=7) answered that doing rehearsal is a good motivational strategy before the competition. They practice as much as possible. They practice to be ready to participate in the competition. This is reflected in the following claims of the students:

- SS6:** “If I have a chance, I need to prepare and do a rehearsal to cut down my anxiety. I can practice it in front of my friend before the competition.”
- SS8:** “Practice with friends at Khmer school. I need to prepare well and note something down before competing. I need to learn more words than others student.”
- SS12:** “In my idea, students have to set schedule to practice and try to study more.”

Discussion

The first purpose of the present study was to investigate factors affecting students in participating public English speaking competition. The questionnaire and the semi-structured interview confirmed that the students agreed with all the factors, but the linguistic factor was the most important reason that blocked them from participating in public English speaking competition, such as: using words that are not appropriate for the situation, pronouncing English words incorrectly, using incorrect English grammar, or not being able to speak English fluently. This finding was in line with several studies that discovered the linguistic factor as a significant role in blocking students from participating in public speaking (Mai, Ngoc & Thao, 2024). The study found that students were unable to control themselves while delivering the speech. Students would be unable to speak correctly if they did not understand grammar. Plus, vocabulary is the most important component of language proficiency because it determines how well learners speak, listen, read, and write (Sela, Rosnija, & Wardah, 2025). In addition, the students' interviews revealed that they lacked self-confidence and experienced anxiety. Shyness and anxiety are the factors that cause them not to join the competition. Students do not believe themselves because of lack of confidence. This study was consistent with Downing, Cooper, Cala, Gin & Brownell (2020) who discovered that students lacked self-confidence, experienced worries, and were afraid of negative judgments. For example, when they did not adequately prepare their speeches, the students felt nervous and anxious. Furthermore, students were unable to control their anxiety while delivering the public speech.

Another purpose of the present study was to explore the students' motivational strategies on participating in English public speaking competition. The questionnaire and the interviews showed that all the strategies in the study are effective and motivational, especially the students consider the language features in the speech, such as grammar, vocabulary, and language expressions. This finding was consistent with some studies which indicated that these students could gain confidence to participate the competition after learning vocabulary and grammar (Argenio, 2023). Additionally, the current study differed from Bhandari (2024) that the students were motivated to participate in an English public speaking competition by selecting interesting topics. Therefore, the researcher can conclude that in order to participate in an English public speaking competition, students need to improve their linguistic skill and follow all the effective strategies.

Conclusion

The study aims to examine factors effecting students' participation in public English-speaking competitions and explore their motivational strategies. Using both quantitative and qualitative methods, the researchers employed questionnaires to analyse students' reluctance to participate and interviews to provide more in-depth insights. The data of the questionnaire was analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (mean scores, percentages, and standard deviations). The findings

revealed that the linguistic factor is the most important among three factors, followed by the physical factor and the environmental factor. Students fear making grammar mistakes, using inappropriate words, and mispronouncing English during public speaking, which hinders fluency. Lastly, the research presented the students' motivational strategies for competing in public English-speaking competitions. The results showed that preparation strategies were effective especially the linguistic improvement was the most significant strategy to motivate students in participating in the competition. It can conclude that in order to participate the public English-speaking competitions, students need to improve their linguistic skill and follow the effective strategies.

Additionally, the researcher makes the recommendations to based lecturer and students on the significance of the study:

1. The lecturer must understand the factors influencing students' public English-speaking experience. They can prepare students for everyday situations by using pairing methods or small groups, explaining appropriate grammar and vocabulary, and correct pronunciation.
2. Students should practice speaking in everyday situations, and participating in an active public speaking forum can help them feel comfortable in unfamiliar environments, reducing anxiety and enhancing their performance.
3. Likewise, because the sample size was small limited to students in a private school, the number of participants in future research should be raised to increase the generalization of the findings, and the data should be collected from and analyze with an experimental study or other studies to evaluate if it is effective for the students.

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